

DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article describes the acmeological competence of the future teacher, the theoretical and practical preparation of the future teacher, and the quality of the integrity of his abilities.

Key words and phrases: socio-economic, independent education, modern outlook, social necessity, digital economy, acmeological position, innovative and digital, market economy, Education and training, scientific-methodical.

Introduction

Today, acmeology penetrates into various professional spheres of social life, it is especially important for the field of pedagogical production. There is a rapid socialization of acmeology. It began to be included in the curricula of various specialties. As educational subjects and teaching aids in acmeology, the first textbooks on this subject are being developed, which will help future specialists to develop professional skills and creative self-realization. mastering theoretical and methodological foundations and methodological ways of achieving, methods of self-improvement, ways to achieve pedagogical excellence in quasi-professional activities in higher educational institutions. The results of the research show that for the first time there is a real opportunity to use and implement the acmeological approach in the training of pedagogical personnel. This situation clearly defines the problem of forming the foundations of acmeological competence in future science teachers as the most important component of professional and pedagogical training at the university. We see the role and importance of this type of professional competence in the development of strategies and tactics for optimal achievement of personal "acme" by each teacher [1:38-40].

In the process of higher education, students understand the basics of pedagogical acmeology and form. There is the actualization of creative and creative activities related to the need-motivational sphere for the professional and personal development of the future teacher, the development of the main components of the teaching profession, and the construction of the position where "I" is a professional.

Further development of the teacher's personal acmeogram is carried out in the process of professional pedagogical activity.

In the years of independence, it was concluded that humanization and socialization of education as the main principles in the training of pedagogues in our republic, the comprehensive educational process aimed at improving the professional training of pedagogues should be implemented taking into account the modern achievements of education at the world level. As a result, an improved system of constantly improving the professional qualifications of professors and teachers and retraining them in accordance with modern requirements was introduced.[2:40]

Materials and Methods

The methodological basis of researching acmeological competence of the future teacher was formed by the following works. V.I. Zvyachinsev, N.A. Koval, T.A. Polozova, Ye.V. Selezneva, V.V.shchyerbina, S.Ye. Shishov, B.G. Ananyev, L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontyev, determinism and development L.I. Ansyferova, V.G. Aseyev, S.L. Rubinstein, systematic approach B.G. Ananyev, B.F. Lomov, E.G. Yudinlar, personal K.A. Abulkhanova Slavekaya, L.I. Ansyferova, V.I. Slobodchikovlar, subjective G.I. Aksenova, V.A. Brushlinsky, A.S. Ochnev, V.A. Petrovsky, V.A. Slastyonins, activity Ye.M. Ivanova, A.N. Leontyev, S.L. Rubinshtein, V.D. Shadrikov, humanist D.A. Belukhin, S.V. Kulnevich, A. Maslow, K. Rodgers, I.A. Yakimanskaya, acmeological A.A. Bodalev, A.A. Derchak, V.G. Zazikin, N.A. Koval, N.V. Kuzmina's approaches are widely described. The individual approach to the teacher's personality is intended to develop the acmeological competence of the future teacher, which is related to the teacher's personality as the main criterion of value, goal, subject, result and efficiency. Because a person always chooses the necessary situations for self-development, these situations appear in his mind with the need for self-awareness, manifestation, improvement, and self-presentation, and the person develops his professional and tries to take the most necessary way for individual development.[3:185-187]

- effective methods of education and training, modern information and communication in order to prevent students and young people from falling under the influence of various information attacks, foreign ideas, committing socially dangerous acts by them, and uniting them in the direction of the future of our country wide use of technologies, taking into account their interest in organizing spiritual and educational events and supporting their initiatives.

Based on these studies and based on the nature of the future teacher's professional and personal development in educational conditions, acmeological competence consists of the following components: need-motivational, cognitive, value-semantic, thinking-activity, professional-activity, social- cooperative and reflective management. The logic of selecting and installing the components of acmeological competence is confirmed by the researches of various authors.

Results

A person's rise to the level of —acme|| as an individual, a person, and a subject of creative activity is often not compatible with each other, or we can only talk about relative compatibility. Acmeology comprehensively illuminates this very important stage that a person goes through in his development - the stage of maturity. It defines the similar and different aspects of different people and, from this point of view, sheds light on the uniqueness of the influence of factors that determine the individual landscape of maturity. And, of course, in these acmeological studies, observing the nature of the interaction of the "physical" and "spiritual" features and characteristics of the "basic essence" of a person takes an important place. According to Shundy, it is important to pay attention to the following acmeological factors in the development of professional competence of leading personnel.[4:17-35]

Figure 1.1.

Age aspect	Aimed at early identification of targets of abilities and opportunities using the tools of pedology (study of children and adolescents), androgygy of adults (including students
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	and professionals) and gerontology (veterans).
Ta'limgaoidjihat	General, professional and continuing education is aimed at the development of knowledge and skills in the system
Professional aspect	It is related to determining the possibilities and results of professional activity in a specific type of activity by determining professional training, psychological preparation for this type of work and the level of social responsibility for the process and its results.
Creative aspect	Determines the success of the implementation of the applied tensions and their professional skills, their improvement to the level of mastery, and the reflexive-innovative possibility of evaluating the social significance of the innovations obtained in the creative process.
Reflexive aspect	The self-awareness of the specialist as a developed "I" and the understanding of the communication partner in the process of menat activity is a system-forming factor that provides the most optimal interaction of the highlighted acmeological aspects of improving the professional skills of a person.

Figure 1. Acmeological factors of professional competence development of future pedagogues

The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological scientific research. From a psychological point of view, competence is "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, consistently develops and possessing a plan of action in complex processes" [5:5] The social content of this concept is very broad, and it is used in almost all areas of production. Competence is equal to the set of modern requirements for the activities of specialists in various fields, the history of its origin is the theory of management, ensuring its effectiveness on the basis of the correct management of the work process in an adequate and fully compatible manner with the purpose of production. , management practice, upper and lower employees in the production process are related to directing the labor behavior to the set goal and efficiency. Accordingly, the competence of a specific employee is consistent with his activity and ability to direct his personal resources to efficiency.[6:343-345]

It is necessary to mention the name of David McClelland (David McClelland) as the founder of the competency-based personnel management approach. The scientist studied the psychological aspects of the characteristics of the production process, and is recognized as the founder of the theory of integrating the motivation of the specialist in production with the production process and goals. According to the scientist, it is precisely the rapid economic development and growth that is responsible for the issue of personnel compensation, and an economic idea does not become effective by itself, but the personnel who make this idea effective and they competence must be present, only companies that can form personnel competence correctly and appropriately will be effective. Therefore, requirements such as

innovative education, interdisciplinary education, business management education, etc., which are integrated with the implementation of the results of scientific and research activities into practice, come to the fore. Historically, the introduction of the concept of competence in the educational system and the acceptance of its importance are divided into stages:

Competencies are the main idea of modernization of education. This idea is not limited to viewing the purpose of education as a system of formation of knowledge, skills and abilities from the framework of existing traditional ideas.[7:5]

The role of competencies in the educational process is defined as the goal of education, the activity-related component of education, the quality indicator of educational activity, and the personal-individual values of the professional.

The founder of the psychology of competence, the English psychologist J. Raven, based on the concept that "competency is a set of competencies", emphasized that there are many of them. J. Raven interpreted the components of competence as characteristics and abilities that allow people to achieve important personal and professional goals, regardless of their nature.[8]

In our opinion, competence is described from the point of view of the functional approach as knowledge, skills and methods of performing directed activities at a high professional level, complex integrative quality of a person, systems that are a tool for his activity and aimed at increasing his efficiency.

And the humanistic approach reveals the personal-professional development of the future teacher as a self-revealing process, and encourages the ability to independently solve the new most important life conflicts, not only of the teacher, but also of the student. This process can show the personal and professional qualities of the teacher aimed at activating the intellectual capabilities of all its participants. The humanistic task of acmeology is that it helps to realize the authenticity of human life, its full manifestation.

Within the acmeological approach, by means of the integration of the principles of the active and personal-active approach, when competence is analyzed taking into account certain laws, conditions and factors, adults ensure a high level of certain activities.

Discussion

The theoretical analysis confirms that competence in acmeological research is determined by the qualities of a person in accordance with the requirements of his profession - professional characteristics, factors affecting the effectiveness of activity. Thus, competence is a necessary condition of a profession, a set of qualities that indicate the effectiveness of a specialist's professional activity and a tool for his personal and professional development.

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work.

Professional competence is evident in the following cases:

- ☒ in complex processes;
- ☒ performing unclear tasks;
- ☒ using conflicting information; - being able to have an action plan in an unexpected situation.

Specialist with professional competence:

- constantly enriches his knowledge;

- learns new information;
- deeply understands the requirements of the era;
- seeks new knowledge;
- processes them and uses them effectively in his practical work.[9]

The competence approach is used to determine the content of education and the quality of specialist training in the higher education system, reveals the integrated description of the quality of the graduate training as the results of education and the interrelated qualities of the individual.

According to our point of view, the competence approach in terms of composition of general professional, professional, general cultural competences should be interpreted as the basis of professional and personal growth of students' and pedagogues' professional competence; general professional competences are determined through their interaction with other groups of competences that are successfully formed in the course of specially organized education, their interdependence, complementing and enriching each other.

It was concluded that the basis of the formation of general professional competencies in future pedagogues should be considered through the organization of their activities outside the classroom, as well as by increasing the educational potential of the didactic system of higher pedagogical education. The essence of the competence approach is manifested in the innovative management of the educational process in the higher pedagogical education system, and at its core lies the formation of competencies - the characteristics and qualities of a person who is a professional. The concepts of "competence" and "competence" appear in different proportions to each other as categories with a specific meaning of the competence approach we are considering.

The conducted theoretical analyzes show that acmeological competence is a multi-level integrated personal-activity quality of a person, which allows a person to set certain tasks and solve them effectively, and self-activation and improvement. and allows solving problems of various complexity levels in the field of self-expression within the framework of various life activities, first of all, in the professional sphere.

Acmeological competence is the professional development of the subject, the ability to make decisive decisions in various life conditions, in various areas, to perform actions that ensure a high level of achievement, to fully realize the existing psychological and acmeological reserves. reflects the ability to convert.

Based on the analysis of psychological-pedagogical literature, we determined the content of acmeological competence for ourselves, that is, if we determine that it is the level of personal requirements of the subject in professional activity, professional requirements, quality goals, professional self-process, it will be wiser.

Determining the essence and content of acmeological competence made it possible to say that acmeological competence is a state of integration of components such as professional creativity, total ownership of a person, reflection, which indicates the emergence of a new qualitative state.

Conclusion

Based on the theoretical analysis, it was concluded that the future teacher, in addition to organizing his personal life strategy based on his knowledge, as well as mastering the methods of predicting and designing the pedagogical process, will make the pedagogical goals concrete and make him pedagogical tasks. he should also know the ways of transformation

into the system. The art of practical mastery of everything requires the clear definition of tasks that fully cover the content of the set goals. Thus, a future teacher who does not know how to predict and make holistic assumptions cannot become a highly qualified specialist. Because the understanding of the goal gives an impulse to activity, mobilizes all the creative forces of a person, leads him to the professional peak, from this it can be concluded that a holistic assumption, recognition as permissible is a decisive element in the acmeological competence of the future teacher.

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